

A large, stylized graphic of a plant branch with several dark green leaves and a thick brown root system, curving across the page. The branch is a light green color, and the leaves are a darker shade of green. The root system is a dark brown color.

ISLANDR Roadmap

Part 3: Portfolio of sites journey

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Summary

This deliverable gives a summary description of the ISLANDR Roadmap journey on portfolio of sites. The ISLANDR Roadmap is a decision-making tool designed to support users engaged in contaminated site management and land redevelopment. Recognising the complexity of the remediation process, the roadmap does not prescribe a rigid set of steps but instead offers structured guidance to navigate key decisions. While it cannot map every possible choice in advance, it provides a clear direction to help users make informed and effective decisions. Adaptable to different contexts, the roadmap can be tailored to deliver user-specific insights, ensuring relevance and practical value for diverse remediation projects. The Roadmap consists of three journeys: single sites, portfolio of sites and diffuse soil contamination, and those journeys are described in separate reports.

Keywords

Sustainable Risk-based Land Management, contaminated sites, brownfields, soil health, circularity, low input remediation, contaminants of emerging concern, wider benefits, wider value, spatial planning, ISLANDR Roadmap

Abbreviations and acronyms

Acronym	Description
CEC	Contaminants of emerging concern
CSM	Conceptual Site Model
PRA.MS	Preliminary Risk Assessment Model for the identification and assessment of problem areas for Soil contamination in Europe European Commission
SPR	Source, pathway, receptor

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ISLANDR project in brief

The Information-based Strategies for Land Remediation, in short ISLANDR, is a multidisciplinary project, which is foremost aimed at supporting the execution of the EU mission: A Soil Deal for Europe.

More specifically, the ISLANDR research activities are designed to provide tools and methods so as to support: (1) the delineation of polluted soils across Europe, (2) an evidence-based assessment of the risks posed by polluted soils, (3) the promotion of sustainable and risk-based land management practices, (4) the inclusion of a wider valuation approach in financial and investment cases, and (5) a closer integration of land contamination and spatial planning decision-making. Lessons learnt and experience gained throughout the project duration will be used to (6) deliver key policy-relevant findings related to the Soil Strategy, the new Soil Health Law, and other areas of policy where soils are crucial.

In order to road-test the project's findings, seven test areas across Europe have been identified. To begin with, the ISLANDR Test Areas (ITAs) will provide a real-world context for the planned research activities. More concretely, the ITAs have been selected to cover different land use types, such as urban, peri-urban, rural, agro-forestry, mining, wetlands and coastal areas. Furthermore, the ITAs are characterized by both point source and diffuse pollution, as well as by different soil pollution types, such as organic, inorganic, as well as contaminants of emerging concern.

Furthermore, ISLANDR brings a dedicated focus to low input remediation, by including test areas impacted by the consequences of the green transition, such as former mining areas. This will ensure that soil remediation will be facilitated even when the cost of remediation is economically marginal or may even be negative. On the one hand, this necessitates a more thorough understanding of low input remediation approaches from a technological perspective, yet it also requires a wider value proposition for investment cases and financial planning.

Key actors, stakeholders and end-beneficiaries are at the epicentre of ISLANDR. Through roundtables in the respective ITAs, the foremost assignment of local actors will be to provide feedback and offer insights as to the robustness and effectiveness of the strategies, frameworks and decision-support tools, as well as on the wider valuation approaches and financing mechanisms to be developed over the course of the project's lifetime. Thus, the Roundtables are foreseen to bring an iterative feedback loop to the research process, with a view to ensure the wider uptake of the project's outcomes and achievements.

Last but not least, local communities in the respective ITAs will be invited to participate in a survey organized both during the early stages and towards the end of the project, as a means to document soil literacy among society thereby bringing insight as to whether the exposure of society to the project's activities on the ground can bring about a strongly desired 'awareness pull' to the benefits to be reaped from healthy soils, thereby leveraging society at large to subscribe to the projects' motto: ISLANDR for Soil Health!

Introduction

The ISLANDR Roadmap is a decision-making tool designed to support users engaged in contaminated site management and land redevelopment. Recognising the complexity of the remediation process, the roadmap does not prescribe a rigid set of steps but instead offers structured guidance to navigate key decisions. While it cannot map every possible choice in advance, it provides a clear direction to help users make informed and effective decisions. Adaptable to different contexts, the roadmap can be tailored to deliver user-specific insights, ensuring relevance and practical value for diverse remediation projects.

This report provides a description of all the activities that are part of the portfolio of sites journey roadmap (table 1).

Table 1. Overview of the different activities per phase, under the portfolio of sites journey

Identification phase
Suspicion of contamination (site scale)
Prioritization of sites: A, B or C sites
Vision/Initiative phase
Preliminary site investigation
Qualitative (preliminary) risk assessment
Exploring preliminary business cases
Look for synergies between sites (portfolio level)
Communication and dissemination strategies
Planning – Jump to the Single site journey

1. Identification

During this phase, one or more suspected areas of soil contamination are found. It includes the regional risk assessment methodology for the prioritisation of potentially contaminated sites.

1.1. Suspicion of contamination (site scale)

Following a trigger, the activity of identifying whether a site is potentially polluted or not is essential to define how to continue. If there is no reason to assume that the site is potentially contaminated, it may proceed directly to the evaluation of reuse strategies. In some cases, the presence of soil contamination can be reasonably excluded based on comprehensive and reliable information on previous land use. However, if some contamination is found, then other steps need to be taken to determine the magnitude and scale of the risks and the necessary steps to take to prevent any harm to humans or the environment.

This activity focuses on investigating any indications of potential contamination and includes reviewing historical contamination information and land uses (e.g. industrial use such as airports and airfields, animal processing, manufacturing, waste treatments, etc) as well as gathering complementing background data that may indicate potential contamination. The latter could include observational data on odour or visible nuisance and reports on potential health impacts, among others.

ISLANDR provides building block on the policy context, soil contamination databases, the identification of hotspots, and geochemical backgrounds to support this activity.

Building block

Policy context

ISLANDR provides a checklist of the most relevant legislation that should be considered in the identification phase of ISLANDR roadmap. The most relevant regulatory instrument is the Soil Monitoring Law (Directive 2025/2360), while depending on the case, additional directives may also be important to consider. The Soil monitoring Law requires that Member States identify potentially contaminated sites, investigate them and assess their risks to human health and the environment, implement the necessary risk management measures and maintain a register on soil contamination.

In the identification phase, one of the key questions can be: “Is the site potentially contaminated and is it clear who is liable?” Regarding the liability issues, the most relevant regulation is the Liability directive (2004/35/CE). However, it is worth noting that this directive is not applicable if contamination took place before 30 April 2007. More information at: [\[ISLANDR D6.1 Report on the policy framework Link\]](#)

Building block

Overview of local soil contamination databases and other data sources

The ISLANDR deliverable on “Overview of local soil contamination databases and other data sources” may support planning and implementing registers/databases suggested in the soil monitoring directive.

In many states, national and regional authorities have already systematically and actively identified all sites where soil contamination is suspected based on the evidence collected through all available means. According to the questionnaire sent to national experts, some countries utilise local soil contamination databases in the prioritisation of investigation- and remediation actions of contaminated sites. The web search showed that the site data in many databases contains information of priority classification. National and regional databases feed to the European-wide indicator used to assess status of local soil contamination and potentially later to national soil contamination registers as required in Soil Monitoring Law proposal. ISLANDR provides a metadata catalogue of these local (and diffuse) soil contamination databases in Europe.

More information at: [\[ISLANDR Deliverable D1.1 Data summary - Overview of Soil Pollution in Europe Link\]](#)

The ISLANDR Metadata Catalogue is available from [\[Link\]](#)

Building block

Data and metadata inventories and interpolation algorithms to produce maps and identify hotspots

National and regional databases were collected for local soil contamination. In many states, national and regional authorities have already systematically and actively identified all sites where soil contamination is suspected based on evidence collected through all available means. ISLANDR provides a metadata catalogue of these local soil contamination European databases.

ISLANDR collected also rare diffuse soil contamination European databases in the metadata catalogue and the review included EU-wide, national and regional monitoring and geochemical mapping databases. Especially in the context of LUCAS (Land Use and Coverage Area frame Survey) (EUSO) and the new Directive on Soil Monitoring and Resilience, spatial soil quality data interpolation methods are needed to identify contamination “hot spots” in Europe that may constitute priority sites for soil remediation. But at the scale of the European Union, soil quality data are often sparse, imprecise or clustered (SIC) and classical interpolation methods are not well suited. ISLANDR has developed a new method of interpolation of spatial soil data that is specifically designed for SIC data. The algorithm is also suitable for interpolation and hot spot detection from more detailed SIC datasets from urban environments. Because the objective is the identification of anomalies, or hot spots, the algorithm avoids the smoothing effects of classical methods, such as kriging with a variogram. The algorithm is also useful for identifying pedogeochemical background values, which are important for the application of the healthy soil criteria of Annex I of the Directive.

Please find more information on databases on local and diffuse soil contamination from the ISLANDR Deliverable D1.1 Data summary - Overview of Soil Pollution in Europe [\[Link\]](#)

Please read more on the interpolation algorithm and hot spot recognition from the ISLANDR Deliverable D1.2 Hot spot identification [\[Link\]](#)

The ISLANDR D1.2 algorithm is available as a binary R package [\[iisdia_1.0.zip\]](#)

The algorithm and its scientific bases are described in: Belbèze, S., Rohmer, J., Guyonnet, D., Négrel, Ph., Tarvainen, T. 2025. Improving spatial interpolation for anomaly analysis in presence of sparse, clustered or imprecise data sets. *Journal of Geochemical Exploration*, 279, 107868.

The ISLANDR Metadata Catalogue is available from [\[Link\]](#)

Building block

Overview of geochemical backgrounds and elements associated with risks

Geochemical background concentration of potentially harmful elements derives from natural geological and pedological processes. In addition to the natural geochemical background concentrations, risk assessment may take into account geochemical baseline concentration (also called background concentration) that includes both natural background and anthropogenic diffuse sources. Geochemical background concentrations and baselines have been studied in European-wide, national and regional soil geochemical mapping programmes, and they contain information on contaminating elements that are associated with risks to human health and the environment.

ISLANDR deliverable D1.1 gives an overview of diffuse soil contamination databases including geochemical mappings [\[Link to D1.1\]](#)

ISLANDR deliverable D1.2 presents a methodology for identifying hotspots in large scale survey or in sparse, imprecise or clustered tests areas.

ISLANDR deliverable D1.3 summarizes the terminology used in ISLANDR reports [\[Link to D1.3\]](#)

ISLANDR Metadata Catalogue gives information on many databases related to geochemical background concentrations [\[Link to ISLANDR metadata catalogue\]](#)

ISLANDR deliverable D2.1 gives a priority list of contaminants of emerging concern, that should be paid attention before other contaminants

1.2. Prioritization of sites: A, B or C sites

National and regional databases for potentially contaminated sites may contain a huge number of records with varying level of information. This information can be valid also for potentially contaminated sites recognized by anomaly identification algorithms. Even when all the potentially contaminated sites should be evaluated, there may be a need for prioritisation of the sites to accelerate remediation of sites that pose the highest risk. Screening and prioritisation processes are crucial for managing contaminated sites at an early stage, when little information is available on each site. For example, already in 2005, the European Environment Agency presented the Preliminary Risk Assessment Model for the identification and assessment of problem areas for Soil contamination in Europe (PRA.MS). This model adopts scoring criteria to rank sites for the identification of problem areas. Specific routines for the assessment of human health and ecological risks are proposed. The approach envisages a pre-screening stage of potentially contaminated sites (Tier 0), based on source size criteria, and a two-tier risk assessment model (Tier 1 and Tier 2) for the identification of problem areas as regards to soil contamination. Tier 1 and Tier 2 can be run sequentially or independently for risk-based scoring of sites pre-selected based on Tier 0. The two-tiered structure of the PRA.MS model allows for the definition of input data and selection of the assessment level based on the quality of the available information.

According to the answers to our ISLANDR questionnaire on local soil contamination databases, about half of the studied European local soil contamination databases have been used either for prioritizing sites for remediation actions or for investigation actions.

ISLANDR provides a building block on the algorithms for the prioritisation of sites, hotspots for a certain region, contaminants of emerging concern (CEC) to support this activity and the regional risk assessment methodology for the prioritisation of potentially contaminated sites.

<p>Building block Overview of algorithms for prioritisation of sites</p> <p>Provides an algorithm for the interpolation of soil contamination data and for the recognition of potentially contaminated anomalous hot spots. This is another way to find potentially contaminated single sites. For example, the ISLANDR Test Area (ITA) in Toulouse, France, is a city with a large study on topsoil contamination, with a relatively large amount of data on soil contamination. Even though there was data, it was scattered, imprecise and clustered, so by using the algorithm for the interpolation of data it is possible to recognize hot spots.</p> <p>More information at: [ISLANDR Deliverable D1.2 Hot spot identification Link] The ISLANDR algorithm is available as a binary R package [iisdia_1.0.zip]</p>
<p>Building block List of CEC to be considered in soils for prioritisation purposes</p> <p>The prioritization method relies on a multi-criteria, risk-based prioritization framework for soil contaminants of emerging concern (CECs) at national and EU scales, structured around the Source–Pathway–Receptor (SPR) model. This prioritisation procedure is based on a structured scoring system. It begins with individual parameter scores, which are used to calculate composite scores for emission potential, environmental fate, and toxicity. These intermediate scores are then aggregated to derive a final prioritisation score, enabling a comparative assessment of CECs based on multiple risk dimensions. The prioritisation Excel tool includes today more than 301 CECs and has produced a prioritised list of the CECs identified as substances of most concern, and a complementary list of substances for which current knowledge is insufficient to allow for a reliable assessment. These results incorporate both risk scores and confidence indicators. This prioritization method the CECs that are in soil, cause the highest risk of large-scale contamination.</p> <p>The excel tool and the CECs lists will be freely available online in the ISLANDR website [link]</p>
<p>Building block Regional risk assessment of potentially contaminated sites</p> <p>Determining whether a site is contaminated requires soil and groundwater investigations, but it is neither feasible nor cost-effective to assess all land across the EU within a short timeframe. Regional level risk assessment (RRA) can support the initial prioritisation of potentially contaminated sites. Maps, historical archives, local knowledge, industrial permits and license records, administrative information, surveys of surface and groundwater quality and site inspections may provide indications that a site is potentially contaminated (Pizzol et al., 2011). Once the list of potentially contaminated sites is available, a prioritization according to relative risk assessment procedures can be performed to select sites where a preliminary soil investigation is first required (Van-Camp et al., 2004). These risk assessment procedures are performed at larger scales (i.e. at regional scale) and should consider that over a regional area, impacts caused by multiple sources are distributed and often multiplied on diverse receptors through different pathways.</p> <p>ISLANDR proposed a GIS-based framework for regional Relative Risk Assessment (RRA) that requires, as input data, an inventory of potentially contaminated sites (PCSs) as this is expected to be progressively available under the Soil Monitoring Law (SML). The methodology follows a stepwise, risk-based logic consistent with Article 43b of the SML, enabling prioritisation before detailed investigations. The framework was successfully tested in the ISLANDR Toulouse Test Area, demonstrating its capacity to rank potentially contaminated sites, thereby supporting early-stage decision-making at the regional scale.</p>

2. Vision / Initiative

During this phase, an actor has an idea that the locations could be used for a particular purpose.

2.1. Preliminary Site investigation

If contamination was found, a preliminary site investigation serves to set up an initial conceptual site model (CSM), identify potential source-pathway-receptor linkages and support qualitative risk assessment. Typically, a preliminary site investigation includes:

- Collecting basic site information;
- Setting objectives, e.g. clarifying intended use, and collating more specific information about past uses and activities (e.g. processes in industrial facilities, chemicals used, waste disposal areas, location of chemical storages);
- Describing land use and setting (e.g., size, topography, microclimate; current and planned use, ecology, access, security, infrastructure, etc.;

- Reviewing contextual, geological, and hydrogeological records for the site, including aquifers and surface water features;
- Site inspection (walkover);
- Identifying material deposits, such as soil stockpiles, that will require management;
- Identifying potential receptors (communities, site users, water, ecology etc.) and potential contaminant pathways (e.g. air);
- Characterisation and 3D delineation of contamination, and whether any of the contaminants is in a priority list;
- Identifying how individual sites fit together in a portfolio.

If any of the potential source-pathway-receptor linkages is missing, and there is little uncertainty about this, then the site is usually designated, from a regulatory point of view, as not contaminated. This designation is strictly related to land use, so record-keeping is needed in case of a change of site use

ISLANDR provides building block on policy triggers to support this activity.

Building block

List of (policy) triggers

Soil Monitoring Law demands that Member States should prepare a list of potentially polluting activities, systematically identify and investigate potentially polluted sites, carry out a site-specific risk assessment for areas found to be contaminated and based on its results ensure that appropriate risk reduction measures are carried out. A baseline report required by the Industrial Emissions Directive may trigger remediation if it shows, at the end of the activity, that the activity has caused significant soil or groundwater contamination. There are also some specific regulations, e.g. regarding mercury and land damage (as per the Environmental Liability Directive), which impose obligations on Member States to manage contaminated sites. ISLANDR provides a list of the relevant legislation to support the preliminary site investigation phase

More information at: [\[ISLANDR D6.1 Report on the policy framework Link\]](#)

2.2. Qualitative (Preliminary) Risk Assessment

The assessment of soil contamination and the need for remediation shall be based on an assessment of the danger or harm caused by the harmful substances in the soil to human health and the environment. A preliminary risk assessment must be carried out when the concentration of a contaminant in the soil exceeds the national or regional threshold value and the regional geochemical baseline concentration. National and regional regulations must be taken into account in the assessment. Usually, there is no need for a preliminary risk assessment when the concentrations are lower than the threshold values and geochemical baseline concentrations unless the assessment is justified for another reason, such as due to contaminants found in other parts of the environment. The application of the threshold value and baseline (or background) concentration requires representative sampling of the soil.

The CSM is updated based on the results of the preliminary risk assessment. If no unacceptable risks are found, the site is deemed uncontaminated. If the risks could be significant, a detailed site investigation and quantitative risk assessment will be usually

required later in the process. However, the detailed site investigation will not be required if the decision is to remediate based on the preliminary risk assessment.

ISLANDR provides building blocks on geochemical backgrounds, on methods and tools for risk assessment, on risk assessment considering soil health and on CEC prioritisation to support this activity.

<p>Building block Overview of geochemical backgrounds and elements associated with risks</p>
<p>Geochemical background concentration of potentially harmful elements derives from natural geological and pedological processes. In addition to the natural geochemical background concentrations, risk assessment may consider geochemical baseline concentration (also called background concentration) that includes both natural and anthropogenic diffuse sources. Geochemical background concentrations and baselines have been studied in European-wide, national and regional soil geochemical mapping programmes, and they contain information on contaminating elements that are associated with risks to human health and the environment as well.</p> <p>More information at: ISLANDR deliverable D1.1 gives overview of diffuse soil contamination databases including geochemical mappings [Link to D1.1] ISLANDR deliverable D1.2 presents a methodology for identifying hotspots in large scale survey or in sparse, imprecise or clustered tests areas. ISLANDR Metadata Catalogue gives information on many databases related to geochemical background concentrations [Link to ISLANDR Metadata Catalogue] ISLANDR deliverable D2.1 gives priority list of contaminants of emerging concern, that should be paid attention before other contaminants</p>
<p>Building block Methods and tools for (preliminary) risk assessment</p>
<p>Provides methods and tools for risk assessment > To present a generic conceptual framework for risk-based assessment for specific sectorial approaches (and associated data needs and sources) to help prioritize sites according to the generic risk they pose.</p> <p>More Information: (numerical tool free access here https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17501164 - Tyrologou, P., Couto, N., Koukouzas, N., Makris, G., Kaija, J., Karatrantou, C., & DERYCKE, V. (2025). LandRisk: A GUI python based software to assess contaminated land risk using Source - Pathway - Receptor setting. Zenodo) - online user guide accessed here : https://youtu.be/XU8UvO_by2E</p>
<p>Building block Risk assessment including soil health</p>
<p>This building block is an extension of risk of land-based management to soil functionality. It provides a decision tree for with soil health descriptors according to land use.</p> <p>More information at: [link]</p>
<p>Building block List of CEC to be considered in soils for prioritisation purposes</p>
<p>The prioritization method relies on a multi-criteria, risk-based prioritization framework for soil contaminants of emerging concern (CECs) at national and EU scales, structured around the Source–Pathway–Receptor (SPR) model. This prioritisation procedure is based on a structured scoring system. It begins with individual parameter scores, which are used to calculate composite scores for emission potential, environmental fate, and toxicity. These intermediate scores are then aggregated to derive a final prioritisation score, enabling a comparative assessment of CECs based on multiple risk dimensions. The prioritisation Excel tool includes today more than 301 CECs and has produced a prioritised list of the CECs identified as substances of most concern, and a complementary list of substances for which current knowledge is insufficient to allow for a reliable assessment. These results incorporate both risk scores and confidence indicators. This prioritization method the CECs that are in soil, cause the highest risk of large-scale contamination.</p> <p>The excel tool and the CECs lists will be freely available online in the ISLANDR website [link]</p>

2.3. Exploring preliminary business cases

During the development of the preliminary business case, roadmap users explore future land uses, how these might deliver value and how they relate to the user’s original interest in the site; a timeline for the remediation and responsible party; and the financial and economic viability of the remediation project. This activity also includes the exploration of possible financial models and partnerships, which will inform the exploration of strategies later on.

In the Portfolio of Sites Journey, this involves an iterative process for exploring socio-economic impacts and preliminary business cases through the identification of:

- Alternative land remediation and re-use scenarios;
- Wider values – including prioritisation of benefits for different groups of stakeholders and possible value creation for investors;
- Linking the project-relevant costs and benefits to specific beneficiaries or payers to identify possible investors for the project and develop the business case
- Relevant timelines for different scenarios;
- Liability transfer/ ownership transfer and who is the developer.

In portfolio management, it is very important to investigate the financial and sustainability benefits and circular economy solutions related to for example, concerted treatment of excavated soils and sharing of equipment, between sites in the portfolio.

To support the exploration of business potential, ISLANDR provides building blocks on sustainable Risk-based Land Management and remediation, criteria for EU funding, quantification and monetary valuation of wider benefits, wider value exploration and prioritisation to support SRBLM, support for developing a business case, and one building block which presents an overview of barriers and solutions.

Building block Criteria for EU funding (taxonomy rules)
<p>EU’s taxonomy regulation sets out four overarching conditions for environmentally sustainable funding and Commission delegated regulation sets technical screening criteria for activity contributing substantially to contamination prevention and control and screening criteria for economic activity causing significant harm to environmental objectives. More information on these regulations is available at: [ISLANDR D6.1 Horizontal policy integration, chapter 4.7.1 / Report on the policy framework link]</p>
Building block Guidance for Sustainable Risk-based Land Management (SRBLM)
<p>The international consensus that has emerged over the past 20-30 years is that decisions regarding contaminated sites should be made based on understanding and managing risks to human health and the wider environment, taking into account the current or planned use of the land. More recently, there has been a growing emphasis that risk management should also align with sustainable development principles. This integrated approach is known as sustainable and risk-based land management (SRBLM), see Figure 1, and is increasingly recognised in international practice, policy, and regulation. Risk management of contaminated sites depends on knowledge of the linkages between sources, pathways and receptors, an estimation of their seriousness and the development of strategies to break linkages that lead to unacceptable risks. The</p>

<p>sustainability of risk management can be considered at multiple stages, including: how best to manage a portfolio of sites, and/or the choices made between different risk management (i.e. remediation) techniques. ISLANDR D3.2 provides overarching guidance on the state of practice for achieving sustainable and risk based land management and highlights how this can be enhanced by consideration of (a) use of low input remediation techniques; (b) circularity - i.e. linkage to a circular economy, (c) maximising the value of restoration to improve its economic case; (d) proper consideration of soil health.</p> <p>More information at: [link]</p>
<p>Building block Support for the quantification and monetary valuation of wider benefits</p>
<p>ISLANDR provides practical and methodological support for the quantification and monetary valuation of wider benefits (economic values) by 1) providing a searchable database containing economic valuation studies and economic values, some of which are suitable for value transfer, and 2) a compilation of economic valuation methods that have been applied in various studies in the brownfield remediation and redevelopment context.</p> <p>More information at: ISLANDR D4.1 [link] and ISLANDR D4.2 [link]</p>
<p>Building block Wider value exploration and prioritisation to support SRBLM</p>
<p>ISLANDR provides support for the envisioning, identifying and prioritising wider values for alternative land use and remediation scenarios in collaboration with relevant stakeholders using a gamified workshop approach based on a checklist of wider values, related indicators and a vision creation exercise. The purpose is to raise awareness among decision-makers and investors that values beyond strictly financial considerations may be critical when deciding how to sustainably remediate and redevelop a site, particularly where the direct financial case is marginal or even negative.</p> <p>More information at: ISLANDR D3.2 [link] and ISLANDR D4.2 [link]</p>
<p>Building block Support for developing a business case</p>
<p>ISLANDR provides support for developing a business case accounting for wider values and evaluating the potential costs and benefits relating to the site remediation and reuse strategies. The purpose is to provide a framework which supports a local project economic analysis to evaluate the 1) potential financial return on investment, 2) potential social return on investment, and 3) opportunities for internalization of wider values as alternative sources of revenue or reduced costs to improve the value proposition for such projects and identification of different financial mechanisms to develop a blended finance strategy.</p> <p>More information at: ISLANDR D4.2 [link]</p>
<p>Building block Overview of barriers and solutions</p>
<p>Countries vary in terms of legal, institutional and financial/economic frameworks when it comes to the remediation and regeneration of contaminated land. Depending on their context and legal, institutional and financial/economic development, all countries in some way experience barriers on their road to land remediation. ISLANDR provides an inventory of barriers countries might experience, depending on their legal, institutional and financial/economic contexts and phase of their remediation journey and proposes possible solutions to overcome those identified barriers. The barrier inventory was conducted through a literature search and complemented with a survey of the ISLANDR participating countries through workshops and conferences.</p> <p>Read more about Barriers and solutions for the reuse of contaminated land and soils in the ISLANDR Deliverable D5.1 Report [Link]</p>

2.4.Look for synergies between sites (portfolio level)

Entries into the roadmap can be from the perspective of applying it to:

1. A portfolio of individual sites, for example evaluating a number of properties as part of a mergers and acquisitions process;
2. An inventory of sites or site data over a wide area, for example considering diffuse pollution monitoring or multiple data points over an urban area.

2.5. Communication and Dissemination Strategies

In this face, there is a need to recognize the relevant stakeholder. The interaction and communication with relevant stakeholders and the broader community during this phase focuses on bringing them on board.

Building block

Harnessing the benefits of the ISLANDR Roadmap

ISLANDR has examined how the ISLANDR roadmap can serve SRBLM of contaminated sites in different European settings

The document draws from qualitative data gathered via focus groups, interviews and a workshop in the ISLANDR test areas (ITAs). Learning from institutional arrangements and practices allows us to identify supportive roles the roadmap can gain in different settings. Although the ITAs necessarily act as mere examples of the diversity of European conditions, the data generated through engagement with regional and national practitioners such as authorities, site owners, consultants and NGO representatives, provide understanding of the types of practical challenges the actors face in their everyday work. These challenges may lower the likelihood of roadmap take-up, but it is also possible that the roadmap, if adopted, could help to tackle key management challenges.

Link [Del6.2 Harnessing the benefits of the ISLANDR roadmap. Policy paper – Proposal of measures to promote institutional adaptability]

ADDITIONAL Building block

Technical publication on sustainable and risk-based land management in practice

The book will provide a single coherent narrative that explains sustainable and risk-based land management from the concepts of land contamination and what triggers action on contaminated sites through to the processes of site investigation, risk assessment, risk management, and the achievement of sustainable approaches to risk management. It also includes a detailed treatment of remediation technologies and how they are implemented, taking particular account of achieving the goals of a circular economy, both in terms of the use of land and the use of soil. It provides an authoritative grounding across all of these topics with extensive citations to sources of more detailed information.

<https://contaminatedland.info/srblm-learning/sbrlm-book>

3. Planning

This wrap-around phase can include multiple activities and is the process by which the vision is elaborated to finally arrive at detailed action plans. Please follow this phase from the single site journey.